

RECYCLABILITY EVALUATION THROUGH EMPIRICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL CRITERIA BASED ON MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-ANALYSIS APPLIED TO TUNDISH WORKING LINING REFRACTORIES

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ABSTRACT

Tundish refractories for the working lining, acting as a sacrificial layer, are commonly composed of highly pure MgO-based materials. Their lifetime spans from few to tens of hours and it is estimated they made up to 20% of the total refractory waste produced during steel production process. Despite this significant amount, recycling of tundish working lining refractories has received scarce attention. Some of the reasons can lie in the abundance of low-cost virgin raw materials and low disposal costs of the largely inert wastes. However, recent environmental sensitivity, circular economy policies, increasing landfill and carbon-tax costs foster attention on spent refractories. Recycling tundish working lining refractories in soil conditioners, roadbed foundations, or slag additives does not exploit the full intrinsic value of the materials. Hence, an additional drawback concerns the opening of the process loop. Even if high value recycling is still a minor share, this alternative solution can mitigate rising prices and supply chain issues generating a closed-loop process taking advantage of the high-purity constituents composing these refractories. The study presented here investigates the influence of empirical and environmental criteria on the recyclability convenience of working lining refractories for the tundish used in steel continuous casting. Three distinct formulations of slurry gunning refractory mixes, exhibiting different particle size distributions and similar chemical composition, were studied. Each of the three mixes has been considered in the new form containing only virgin raw materials, and with various fractions of secondary raw material. MgO and impurities (SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃) content, open porosity, water requirement, permeability, corrosion resistance, and slag infiltration depth were experimentally determined and considered as empirical criteria. Literature data and LCA open-source databases have been used to estimate carbon footprint, energy consumption and production costs of the refractory mixes and taken into account for the environmental criteria. The influence of criteria weights variation has been assessed and exploited to generate objective functions of best convenience.

CONTEXT

The combination of EU Green Deal challenging targets for 2050 and geopolitical focus on critical raw materials and processing technologies is driving a profound evolution in the energy-intensive steel industry.¹ This exerts pressure also on the associated refractory industry to develop more sustainable and circular solutions. Basic monolithic refractories, such as magnesia-based lining refractories for tundish, represent a focal point in a greener economy considering their major share as refractory wastes, and the significant energy and carbon

footprint associated to the dead-burnt magnesia production.^{2,3} As a result, the research on closed-loop reuse and recycling of tundish working lining refractories presents an opportunity to mitigate environmental treats, conserve critical raw materials, reduce landfill, and foster circular economy principles.⁴ Realizing the full potential of tundish refractory wastes, particularly in high-demanding applications, presents intricate challenges. The combination of appropriate physico-chemical properties of the recycled fractions, technical feasibility of sorting and prioritizing, economic viability, process safety, environmental advantage of secondary raw materials generate complexities in closed-loop recycling feasibility determination.⁵ Addressing the inherent multifaced complexity arising from these interdependent and often competing technical, economic, and environmental parameters necessitates a rigorous evaluation methodology. The multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) provides a robust framework for problems involving conflicting objectives.⁶ This study employs MCDA to conduct a comparative assessment of the recycling feasibility across three different slurry spray MgO-based tundish working lining formulations. Specifically, a tailored MCDA model has been developed and applied, implementing the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). This specific method offers a ranking of refractory alternatives by evaluating their performance against ideal best and worst solutions.⁷ A critical element in our analysis involves performing sensitivity assessments through the systematic variation of criteria weights. This allows the exploration of how shifts in strategic priorities, operative requirements, or potential future policy landscapes might influence the relative ranking.

INTRODUCTION

Tundish Working Linings

Working lining materials, also referred as basic monolithics, used in steelmaking tundishes are typically slurry spray or dry vibratable refractory mixes applied on the surface of the safety lining. The working lining forms the sacrificial layer directly in contact with molten steel during continuous casting, and together with insulation and safety, composes the lining refractory assembly that is commonly adopted for steel continuous casting tundish (Fig. 1).

The working lining refractories have been chosen because of their “disposable” nature. The reasons for that are to maintain steel cleanliness (preventing contamination from a sequence specific steel grade, to the next), ensure operational safety, and optimize thermal performance. Working lining refractories are applied forming a layer ranging generally from 40 to 80 mm, depending on technical considerations. After a casting sequence (typically several hours), the tundish is taken offline

Fig. 1 Continuous casting elements (ladle, tundish, cooling) and magnification of tundish refractory lining system.

and the remaining steel skull along with the entire working lining is mechanically removed (technically defined as deskulling) by turning the tundish upside-down. The process leads to the generation of large volumes of spent, highly pure, refractory wastes. In fact, the primary raw material (in the range between 60 to 80 %) is typically dead-burned magnesia (DBM), produced by calcining natural magnesite ($MgCO_3$) at very high temperatures (higher than 1500 °C). Such high purity presents a significant theoretical potential in the secondary raw material for closed-loop recycling. Nowadays, there is not a well-established processing route to keep high the value of spent basic monolithics. Most of the practices documented in literature involve the downscaling in non-critical applications and open-loop recycling for example as slag conditioners, refractory lids, top rings, soil fertilizers and roadbeds.⁸

Avoiding the primary production of DBM through effective recycling of spent MgO-based materials aligns directly with the net-zero objectives by reducing energy consumption, conserving virgin resources, and mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the high share of waste generated by this spent basic monolithics can exert a marked impact on the refractory circular economy. Hence, assessing the trade-offs between the quality (purity) required, cost of processing, properties of the refractory containing secondary raw materials, and the environmental benefit makes this an ideal case for applying the MCDA methodology.

Multi Criteria Decision Analysis & TOPSIS

The multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) consists of a technique designed to support decision-makers faced with evaluating multiple possible solutions (defined as alternatives) based on numerous, often conflicting, criteria. The criteria are the measurable outcomes (performances) associated to that specific alternative in a particular frame. Thus, MCDA aim to identify a preferred alternative, or rank of alternatives, by considering trade-offs across all relevant criteria. A MCDA involves commonly six steps:

1. Goal definition;
2. Alternatives identification;
3. Relevant criteria determination;

4. Data collection;
5. Weights allocation;
6. Algorithm application and alternatives ranking.

The last step, algorithm application, defines the multi-criteria decision methodology. In our case, the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is the method selected. Its core consists in the identification of the preferred alternative as the one possessing the shortest geometric distance from the best ideal solution and the longest geometric distance from the worst ideal solution in a multi-dimensional criteria space. The most preferred solution is identified with a scoring system ranging from 0 to 1 depending on the proximity to the ideal solutions. The ideal best solution is a hypothetical alternative that possesses the best possible values for all considered criteria (e.g., maximum purity, maximum thermochemical resistance, minimum production cost, minimum carbon footprint impact). The contrary holds for the worst ideal solution.

The adoption of TOPSIS over other techniques, such as ELECTRE, PROMETHEE, or SAW, was driven by its computational simplicity, effective data handling, logic clarity, reproducibility, and widespread application and acceptance in various fields.⁹

MATERIALS & METHODS

Three distinct formulations of slurry spray refractory mixes, named WL1, WL2 and WL3 with similar chemical composition were studied. Each of the three mixes has been considered in the new form, containing only virgin raw materials, and with increasing amount of secondary raw material (SRM), 20 and 50 %. The SRM was taken on the field after deskulling from post-mortem samples of the same refractory mix in order to promote the closed-loop recycling practice. To obtain the SRM, the spent refractory was subjected to low energy hand crushing followed by mechanical sieving. Only the particles greater than 63 μm were substituted in the refractory mix. The addition of SRM fractions was congruent with the virgin mix particles size distribution curve.

Chemical composition for the new mixes and fully graded SRM was measured with XRF Bruker S8 Tiger. Fused beds were obtained mixing 1.0 g of representative sample with 10.0 g of $Li_2B_4O_7$ as flux.

Later, the materials have been mixed with fresh tap water, the percentage depended on the workability and the refractory suppliers' suggestions. A planetary mixer was used at intermediate speed for maximum time of 5 minutes. The wet mixes were then cast in bricks (160x40x40 mm³), left dry in atmospheric conditions for 24 hours and then fired at 1550 °C in Nabertherm LHT04/17 with 2 hours dwell at maximum temperature, for later characterization. Permanent linear change (PLC) was assessed following the standard ASTM C113, from green state (after 24h of mixing let in atmospheric conditions) to 1550 °C. Pores size distribution was obtained

Tab. 1: Chemical composition of the three tundish working lining mixes considered.

Composition (%)	WL1	WL1 - SRM	WL2	WL2 - SRM	WL3	WL3 - SRM
MgO	76.5	70.6	75.0	62.7	73.6	68.1
SiO ₂	18.1	18.4	16.7	27.3	17.9	18.2
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.6	6.2	2.8	5.9	3.1	7.0
CaO	1.6	2.1	2.3	4.8	1.3	1.8
Al ₂ O ₃	1.2	1.0	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.4

through mercury intrusion porosimetry with Micrometrics AutoPore IV 9500. Permeability test was conducted in transient state at hydrostatic confinement pressure of 10 MPa with instrument developed by Centrale Lille and available in the Belgian Ceramic Research Center (BCRC). The pressure drop for permeability calculation was considered 0.05 MPa. The thermal conductivity of the mixes was estimated based on the intrinsic property of each oxide, and the global composition (retrieved from Rietveld refinement of powder XRD data), and considering the pore fraction using the Landauer model. Industrial tundish slag conditioner, with basicity defined as $(\text{CaO}+\text{MgO})/\text{SiO}_2=0.24$, was used for the corrosion cup test. The test was performed according to the Standard CEN/TS 15418. Experimental values for mixes containing high share of SRM (80 and 100 %) were obtained through interpolation of the experimental data. Carbon footprint was calculated from the single minerals $\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}}$ /ton emissions reported in literature and weight averaged based on the mix composition.¹⁰ Production cost was obtained from refractory consultants' reports (referred to North America market) and is referred to solely production, taxes free, without including services. The evolution of carbon footprint and production cost according to share of SRM used in the mix was calculated based on the particle size distribution curve, the binder type and quantity, and the mineralogical composition. For the sensitivity analysis of TOPSIS, it was conducted by choosing a specific criterion and varying discreetly its weight from 0.1 to 0.88. The remaining weight fraction was divided equally and assigned to the remaining criteria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the influence of the selected criteria weights on the recyclability convenience through TOPSIS method.

Initially, the three “New” mixes contain only virgin raw material and the addition of SRM (its share) is identified by the “+ 20%”, for example, “WL1 + 20%”, this creates the spectrum of refractory mixes constituting the alternatives for the MCDA. Later, the criteria have been divided in three categories: property, performance, and environmental. As property criteria, the following parameters were considered: the purity of the system depicted by the share of MgO and the amount of silica and iron oxides ($\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_x\text{O}_y$), the water demand for application, a global pore size indicator (D_{50}) and the permeability of the material. For the performance criteria, were chosen PLC, thermal conductivity at room temperature, and corrosion rate. Carbon footprint from cradle to cradle, and the production cost of the refractory mix were taken into account as environmental criteria. Literature and LCA open-source databases have been considered for the environmental criteria estimation.

The composition of the new dry mixes and of the SRM, containing all grain size, was experimentally determined (Tab. 1). The three new systems present similar composition. WL1 resulted to be the purest recipe in terms of MgO quantity. Comparable amount of SiO_2 and iron oxides impurities have been detected. For the SRM, an increase in iron content from the new material to the SRM was observed. A particular case is represented by WL2 for which the silica share increases significantly in the SRM with respect to the new one. This can be related to several factors, among them the casted steel grade and the slag/flux used in the tundish from which we collected

the post-mortem material. Mineralogical composition was also investigated in order to retrieve the phase composition of the materials (Fig. 2). They proved to be a typical basic-monolithic refractory mix based on $\text{MgO-Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4$ (periclase-forsterite) composition. The XRD patterns refinement also allowed to identify different impurities deriving from the raw materials, for the new mix, and from the casting process, for the SRM. In this paper we focus only on the qualification and quantification of quartz, hematite and magnetite because of their known tendency to create eutectics at high temperatures in the system of refractory studied. Further details regarding the experimental results are beyond the scope of this document. The resulting alternatives-criteria matrix is not reported here. The TOPSIS algorithm requires in first instance to assign weights to the considered criteria. In this study, we first considered an equally weighted TOPSIS. More precisely, the weights for the 10 criteria have been considered equal to 0.1. In such a context, no specific strategy is applied but the selection of criteria assumes a pivotal role in influencing the outcome. For the ideal solutions calculation, the MgO content was designated as the only criterion to be maximized. All the remaining criteria have been considered to be minimized in the ideal best case. Contrarywise for the ideal worst solutions. The application of TOPSIS under an equally weighted scenario (all criteria have a weight assigned of 0.1), corresponding to the left points in Fig. 3, revealed that WL1 incorporating 20% SRM (WL1+20%) emerged as the most favorable alternative. The virgin WL1 mix showed a comparable score, indicating minimal variation in overall attributes with this level of SRM. Similarly, WL3+20% ranked highly to the same mix, preceding its virgin raw material containing counterpart. Conversely, all WL2 formulations demonstrated lower preference, with scores monotonically declining as SRM content increased, highlighting a sensitivity to SRM addition. Generally, for the better-performing base mixes (WL1, WL3), lower SRM additions (20%) were preferred or on par with virgin material, while higher SRM levels led to decrease overall scores. This suggests that moderate SRM incorporation is viable, especially if the base refractory design is robust, confirming the already established literature.

To understand the impact of different strategic priorities, a sensitivity analysis was performed by systematically varying the weight of the selected criteria. Here we report the outcomes of only one criterion. Impurities ($\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$) content has been selected for the weights' sensitivity analysis

Fig. 2: XRD spectra of the three tundish working linings in the new state and the SRM resulting from the respective post-mortem (in red impurities-related peaks).

(Fig. 3). A more comprehensive publication will be available soon. Weights varied from 0.1 to 0.88. The remaining weights were equally distributed to the remaining criteria. Increasing the weight for impurity content logically favored virgin material formulations (WL1-New, WL3-New) and those with minimal SRM (WL1+20%), which became the top-ranked alternatives. The final top three alternatives resulted to be, in order, WL1 - New, WL1 + 20% and WL3 – New. For almost all the alternatives the ranking variation showed a sigmoidal behavior with an inflection point around 0.4 of the criterion weight. WL1, being the purest starting mix, as observed before, led to a general increase in the ranking of its alternatives. For the WL2-based refractory mixes a sigmoidal behavior is observed also and higher rank increase is observed, especially for the mixes containing low share of SRM. The WL2 alternative containing 100% of SRM showed, on the contrary, a marked decrease in score making it the least preferred option. Additionally, as the impurity criterion gain importance the spectrum of scores for the alternatives gets wider.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that there is no universal "best" recycling strategy for tundish working lining refractories. The optimal level of SRM incorporation is a complex function of the specific base refractory formulation, the quality of the SRM, and, critically, the strategic priorities (physico-chemical properties, technical performance, or environmental targets) of the steel plant. The TOPSIS approach, coupled with sensitivity analysis, provides a powerful and flexible tool for navigating these complexities. For the investigated systems, a moderate SRM addition (around 20%, potentially up to 50% for specific formulations like WL1, if environmental concerns are paramount) appears to offer a balanced compromise. However, careful

Fig. 3: TOPSIS sensitivity analysis according to impurities ($\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$) criterion weight for the refractory working lining alternatives containing virgin raw material ("NEW") and containing various amount of SRM with particles $>63 \mu\text{m}$, until the full substitution of SRM "+100%".

characterization and tailored decision-making are essential to truly harness the potential of refractory recycling in a circular economy. Future work could extend this by incorporating dynamic economic analysis exploring the impact of SRM processing techniques.

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